

BOSHQARUV FUNKSIYALARI EKSPONENSIAL CHEGRALANISHLI QUVISH MASALASI

S. I. Uralova

V.I.Romanovskiy nomidagi Matematika instituti tayanch doktoranti.

O‘zbekiston.

Quvish masalasi differensial o‘yinlarda integral chegralanishli hol uchun parallel yaqinlashish strategiyasidan foydalanilgan holda ko‘plab ishlarda to‘la hal qilingan (masalan [1-7]). Biz ushbu ishda quyidagi differensial o‘yinda quvish masalasini ko‘raylik.

Masalaning qo‘yilishi: Faraz qilaylik R^n fazoda ikkita o‘yinchi harakatlanayotgan bo‘lsin. Ulardan biri P quvlovchi boshqasi esa E qochuvchi bo‘lsin deymiz. P quvlovchi E qochuvchini ta‘qib qilayotgan bo‘lsin. Hamda ularning harakat dinamikalari R^n fazoda quyidagi (1)-(2) sistema bilan berilgan bo‘lsin:

$$P: \dot{x} = u, \quad x(0) = x_0, \quad (1) \quad E: \dot{y} = v, \quad y(0) = y_0, \quad (2)$$

bu yerda har bir t vaqtda, $x(t)$ P quvlovchining, $y(t)$ esa E qochuvchining harakat holati vektorlaridir; x_0 va y_0 -mos ravishda bu vektorlar P quvlovchi va E qochuvchining boshlang‘ich holatidir hamda $x_0 \neq y_0$; Quyidagi akslantirishni qanoatlantiruvchi $u(\cdot): [0, +\infty) \rightarrow R^n$ va $v(\cdot): [0, +\infty) \rightarrow R^n$ uzluksiz hamda o‘lchanuvchi funksiyalar mos ravishda P quvlovchi va E qochuvchining boshqaruv funksiyalaridir, ular quyidagi eksponensial chegaralanish qanoatlantiradi deb faraz qilamiz, ya‘ni $u(\cdot) \in U$ va $v(\cdot) \in V$:

$$\int_0^t |u(s)|^2 ds \leq \rho^2 e^{2kt}, \quad t \geq 0, \quad (3) \quad \int_0^t |v(s)| ds \leq \sigma^2 e^{2kt}, \quad t \geq 0,$$

(4)

bu yerda ρ, σ, k lar musbat parametrlar(sonlar) hamda U - (3)-tengsizlikni qanoatlantiruvchi barcha $u(\cdot)$ funksiyalar to‘plami; V -(4)-tengsizlikni qanoatlantiruvchi barcha $v(\cdot)$ funksiyalar to‘plami (qarang [3.b-910]).

Yendi (1)-(4) foydalanib biz o‘yichilarning harakat trayektoriyalarini topamiz (qarang [6.b-70]):

$$x(t) = x_0 + \int_0^t u(s)ds, \quad y(t) = y_0 + \int_0^t v(s)ds.$$

Yendi biz quyidagi ishlar [1-7] dagi kabi (1)-(4) o'yin uchun asosiy ta'riflarni keltirib o'tamiz.

Ta'rif 1. $u(t, v): R^+ \times R^n \rightarrow R^n$ uzluksiz funksiya quvlovchining strategiyasi deyiladi, agarda u - Borel o'lchanuvchi funksiya bo'lsa.

Ta'rif 2. Strategiya u - tutishni $T(u)$ vaqt davomiyligida tugatadi deyiladi, qachonki har bir $v(\cdot) \in V$ uchun $x(t^*) = y(t^*)$, $t^* \in [0, T(u)]$ bo'lsa, bu yerda $(x(t^*), y(t^*))$ juftlik quyidagi

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}(t) = u(t, v(t)), & x(0) = x_0, \\ \dot{y}(t) = v(t), & y(0) = y_0 \end{cases}$$

sistemaning yechimidir.

Ushbu masalada biz quvlovchi uchun parallel yaqinlashish ya'ni Π strategiyani taklif qilamiz (qarang [1, b-35]).

Ta'rif 3. Har bir $v(\cdot) \in V$ uchun $z(t)$ vektor:

$$z(t) = z_0 \Lambda(t, v(\cdot)), \quad \Lambda(0, v(\cdot)) = 1$$

bo'lsa, u holda strategiya u quvlovchining parallel yaqinlashish yoki Π strategiyasi deb ataladi, bu yerda $z(t) = x(t) - y(t)$, $\Lambda(t, v(\cdot))$ esa uzluksiz hamda kamayuvchi funksiyadir.

Ta'rif 4. Quyidagi (5)-funksiya

$$u(t, v) = v - \lambda(t, v) \xi_0, \quad \lambda(t, v) = \max \{0, 2 \langle v, \xi_0 \rangle + \bar{\delta}_0 e^{2kt}\}$$

(5)

quvlovchining Π -strategiyasi deyiladi, agarda (1)-(4) o'yinda $\rho \geq \sigma$ bo'lsa, bu yerda, $\delta_0 = \frac{\rho^2 - \sigma^2}{|z_0|}$, $\xi_0 = \frac{z_0}{|z_0|}$, $\langle v, \xi_0 \rangle - v$ va ξ_0 vektorlarning skalyar ko'paytmasi.

Yeslatma 1: $|u(t, v)| = |v(t)| + \bar{\delta}_0 e^{2kt} \lambda. \quad (6) \quad \lambda = \frac{|z_0|}{t^*}. \quad (7)$

Teorema 1. Agar $\rho > \sigma$ bo'lsa va $\Lambda(t) = 0$ tenglama musbat yechimga ega bo'lsa, u holda quvlovchi (5)- Π strategiya yordamida (1)-(4) o'yinda qochuvchini

$$[0, T] \text{ vaqt oralig'ida tutadi, bu yerda } \Lambda(t) = 1 - \frac{\delta}{2k|z_0|} (e^{2ks} - 1) + \frac{2\sigma}{|z_0|} \sqrt{t} e^{kt}.$$

Isbot. Faraz qilaylik qochuvchi ixtiyoriy $v(\cdot) \in V$ boshqaruvda harakat qilyotgan bo'lsin, quvlovchi esa (5) - Π strategiyadan foydalansin, u holda (1)-(4) o'rniga quyidagi o'yinni ko'ramiz:

$$\dot{z} = \mathbf{u}(t, v(t)) - v(t) = -\lambda(t, v(t))\xi_0, \quad z(0) = z_0 \mathbf{1}_0$$

Yuqoridagi masalani yechish orqali quyidagi yechimni olamiz:

$$z(t) = \Lambda(t, v(\cdot))z_0,$$

(8)

bu yerda $\Lambda(t, v(\cdot)) = 1 - \frac{1}{|z_0|} \int_0^t \lambda(s, v(s)) ds$.

Quyidagi tengsizlikka ko'ra (qarang [2.760-b])

$$\int_0^t \max\{0, \varphi(s)\} ds \geq \max\left\{0, \int_0^t \varphi(s) ds\right\},$$

bu yerda $\varphi(s)$ ixtiyoriy integralanuvchi funksiya, biz quyidagi xulosaga kelamiz:

$$\int_0^t \max\{0, 2\langle v(s), \xi_0 \rangle + \bar{\delta}_0 e^{2ks}\} ds \geq \max\left\{0, \int_0^t (2\langle v(s), \xi_0 \rangle + \bar{\delta}_0 e^{2ks}) ds\right\}.$$

Oxirgi natijaga ko'ra

$$\Lambda(t, v(\cdot)) \leq 1 - \frac{1}{|z_0|} \int_0^t (2\langle v(s), \xi_0 \rangle + \bar{\delta}_0 e^{2ks}) ds.$$

Quyidagi belgilashni kiritamiz

$$\bar{\Lambda}(t, v(\cdot)) = 1 - \frac{1}{|z_0|} \int_0^t (2\langle v(s), \xi_0 \rangle + \bar{\delta}_0 e^{2ks}) ds.$$

$\bar{\Lambda}(t, v(\cdot))$ funksiya $t \geq 0$ argument bo'yicha monoton kamayuvchi ekanligini ko'rish qiyin emas, shunga ko'ra uni yuqoridan baholaymiz:

$$\Lambda(t, v(\cdot)) \leq 1 - \frac{\delta}{2k|z_0|} (e^{2ks} - 1) + \frac{2}{|z_0|} \int_0^t |v(s)| ds.$$

(4)-tengsizlikdan hamda Koshi-Bunyakovskii tengsizligidan foydalangan holda, quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz

$$\int_0^t |v(s)| ds \leq \left(\int_0^t ds\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\int_0^t |v(s)|^2 ds\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} = \sqrt{t} \left(\int_0^t |v(s)|^2 ds\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \leq \sigma \sqrt{t} e^{kt}.$$

Oxirgi tengsizlikdan biz quyidagi natijalarni olamiz:

$$\Lambda(t, v(\cdot)) \leq 1 - \frac{\delta}{2k|z_0|} (e^{2ks} - 1) + \frac{2\sigma}{|z_0|} \sqrt{t} e^{kt} \quad \text{va} \quad \Lambda(t, v(\cdot)) \leq \Lambda(t).$$

$\rho > \sigma$ shartga ko'ra shunday T vaqtda $\Lambda(T) = 0$ bo'ladi va shunday mavjud $t^* \in [0, T]$ vaqt uchun $\Lambda(t^*, v(\cdot)) = 0$ bo'ladi. $\Lambda(t^*, v(\cdot)) = 0$ va (8) tenglikdan foydalangan holda biz quyidagi xulosaga kelamiz.

$$z(t^*) = 0 \quad \text{yoki} \quad x(t^*) = y(t^*)$$

Yendi biz (5)- Π -strategiyani joizligini, ya'ni (3) tengsizlikni $[0, t^*]$ vaqt oralig'ida qanoatlantirishini ko'rsatamiz. Faraz qilaylik qochuvchi V to'plamdan ixtiyoriy $v(\cdot)$ boshqaruv tanlasin, u holda (6) va (7) dan foydalangan holda (5)- Π strategiyani joizligini quyidagicha ko'rsatamiz:

$$|u_{\text{exp}}(t, v(t))| = |v(t)| + \frac{\rho^2 - \sigma^2}{|z_0|} \lambda_{\text{exp}} e^{2kt}.$$

Oxirgi tenglikni ikkkala tomonini $[0, t^*]$ bo'yicha integrallaymiz

$$\int_0^{t^*} |u(t, v(t))|^2 ds \leq \int_0^{t^*} |v(s)|^2 ds + \int_0^{t^*} \frac{\rho^2 - \sigma^2}{|z_0|} \lambda e^{2ks} ds.$$

(4) tengsizlikka ko'ra biz quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz

$$\int_0^{t^*} |u(s, v(s))|^2 ds \leq \sigma^2 e^{2kt^*} + \int_0^{t^*} \frac{\rho^2 - \sigma^2}{|z_0|} \lambda e^{2ks} ds.$$

(7) tenglikdan foydalanib, quyidagi natijani olamiz

$$\int_0^{t^*} |u(s, v(s))|^2 ds \leq \sigma^2 e^{2kt^*} + \frac{\rho^2 - \sigma^2}{|z_0|} \lambda e^{2kt^*} \int_0^{t^*} ds = \sigma^2 e^{2kt^*} + (\rho^2 - \sigma^2) e^{2kt^*}.$$

Demak, $\int_0^{t^*} |u(s, v(s))|^2 ds \leq \rho^2 e^{2kt^*}$. Teorema isbotlandi.

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